

m.m.p. 220°; ethyl dithiobiuret (3 g), ethyl thiuret HBr (1.2 g), m.p./m.m.p. 154°.

Reaction of methyl dithiobiuret (1) with propyl bromide in n-propanol. Formation of 4-S-propyl-1-methylisodithiobiuret HBr and methyl thiuret hydrobromide (3): A mixture of methyl dithiobiuret (3 g), n-propanol (20 ml) and propyl bromide (1.8 g) was refluxed for 1.5 h. 4-S-Propyl-1-methylisodithiobiuret HBr was precipitated with dry ether, when an oil was obtained which was taken up in n-propanol (20 ml), the solution refluxed for 6 h and worked up as described earlier to give 3 (R = Me; 1.1 g).

Propanolic solution from the above experiment was chromatographed on a Toshniwal RL-04 gas chromatograph using carbowax-400 M having column temp. 90°, injection port, 120° and detector, 120°, (FID)-sensitivity $10^{-8} \times 1$; the retention time for propyl bromide, 4 min; n-propanol, 11 min.

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks of the authors are due to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support, to Dr. A. N. Inamdar, Director and Dr. V. S. Darshane, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Institute of Science, Bombay, for facilities.

References

1. M. H. DAMLE, Ph.D. Thesis, Nagpur University, 1976.
2. E. FROMM and D. VON GONEZ, *Justus Liebig's Ann. Chem.*, 1907, 355, 196.
3. R. E. ALLEN, R. S. SHELTON and V. M. G. CAMPEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 158.
4. V. K. VERMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 116.
5. M. S. CHANDE and G. BHASKARAIYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 38.
6. M. S. CHANDE and N. P. SHERGIRI, *Indian Council Chem.*, in the press.
7. S. N. DIXIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 44.
8. V. K. VERMA and C. P. JOSHUA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 988.

Occurrence of (+)-Vasicinone in *Adhatoda vasica* Nees

RAJLAKSHMI POI (née CHAUDHURY)
and
N. ADITYACHAUDHURY*

Department of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science,
Bidhan Chandra Kriishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 12 November 1987, revised 10 June 1988,
accepted 29 July 1988

THE leaves of *Adhatoda vasica* Nees (Acanthaceae) are used in the indigenous system of medicine¹. The earlier workers isolated (-)-vasicinone and (±)-vasicinone from the leaves of *A. vasica*

Nees^{2,3}. We now report for the first time the occurrence of (+)-vasicinone in the leaves of *A. vasica*.

The concentrated MeOH extract of defatted leaves of *A. vasica* (a voucher specimen is preserved in our laboratory) was churned with 5% citric acid and filtered. The filtrate was shaken with CHCl_3 and removed the non-alkaloidal matter and then made alkaline with cold ammonia to pH 9 and extracted with CHCl_3 . The CHCl_3 solution was extracted with 1% HCl. The acidic solution was made alkaline with cold ammonia (pH 9) and extracted with chloroform. On concentration, the chloroform solution yielded (±)-vasicine, m.p. 198–99°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} \text{EtOH} \pm 0^{\circ 2,4}$. The mother liquor upon column chromatography over silica gel afforded another alkaloid, crystallising from chloroform–ethyl acetate, m.p. 201–02° $[\alpha]_D^{25} \text{EtOH} + 148^{\circ}$ ($C=1.35 \text{ mg ml}^{-1}$), showing ir spectrum similar to that reported for vasicinone⁵. Its uv, nmr and mass spectra were in concordance with those reported for (-)-vasicinone. However, the $[\alpha]_D$ of our isolated vasicinone was (+)ve and that of the authentic sample was found to be (-)ve. Further, acetylation of (+)-vasicinone with acetic anhydride–pyridine followed by chromatography over silica gel yielded the acetyl derivative, m.p. 134–35° $[\alpha]_D^{25} \text{CHCl}_3 + 10^{\circ}$ ($C=1 \text{ mg ml}^{-1}$) showing ir absorptions at 1755 and 1240 cm^{-1} (OCOCH_3). Thus the optical rotations of vasicinone and its corresponding acetyl derivative proved that vasicinone isolated from *A. vasica* occurs in (+) form.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (R.P.). They also thank Dr. M. P. Jain, Scientist, Regional Research Laboratory for a gift of (-)-vasicinone and Dr. D. S. Bhakuni of C.D.R.I. for spectral analysis.

References

1. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", B. SINGH and M. P. SINGH, 1975, Vol. III p. 1900.
2. D. R. MEHATA, J. S. NARAYAN and R. M. DESAI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, 28, 445.
3. I. HELLBORON, A. H. COOK, H. M. BANBURY and D. H. HAY, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Eyre and Spottishoode, London, 1965, Vol. V, p. 5686.
4. B. K. CHOUDHURY and P. BHATTACHARYYA, *Phytochemistry*, 1985, 24, 3080.
5. K. L. DEAR, M. P. JAIN, S. K. KOUL and C. K. ATAL, *Phytochemistry*, 1981, 20, 319.